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Elucidating the impact of gas transport on high-performing air electrodes: a 1D physically based model unveiling the correlation between microstructure and impedance response

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Abstract

A 1D physically based model of high-performing air electrodes for solid oxide cells is used to unravel the physical mechanisms lying behind the resistive peaks observed in experimental impedance data, posing particular attention to the low-frequency contribution. In particular, the latter is commonly observed when analyzing the impedance response of high-performing air electrode materials, but its physical interpretation is still questioned. The model construction is grounded on the microstructural characteristics of conventional screen-printed electrodes. These properties were extracted by combining the statistical analysis of experimental 2D images taken with a scanning electron microscope with a validated microstructural model able to generate synthetic 3D reconstructions of homogeneous electrode architectures. The implemented electrochemical model is tailored to the specific characteristics of a reference high-performing SmBa_{0.8}Ca_{0.2}Co₂O_{5+δ} electrode material. Specifically, the model was used to reproduce its stationary and dynamic behavior in the temperature range 650 °C and 750 °C, with an inlet oxygen partial pressure from 0.1–1 atm. The performed simulations unravel the physical mechanisms lying behind the resistive contributions emerging from the impedance data. In particular, the effect of gas transport is analyzed in detail to understand the impact of the electrode microstructure on its electrochemical behavior. A sensitivity analysis of the effective gas diffusion coefficient highlighted that, in the investigated operating conditions, the electrochemical performance of classic screen-printed air electrodes is not limited by the gas diffusion. In contrast, the low-frequency contribution evidenced in the Nyquist plot was addressed to the impact of gas conversion. The developed electrochemical model successfully completes the correlation between microstructural and electrochemical properties and the results included in this study can be extended to different electrode materials tested in similar operating conditions.

Nomenclature

Symbols

$A_{\text{electrode}}$	Electrode surface area (m ²)
C_{ct}	Charge transfer capacitance at the interface SBCCO/porosity (F·m ⁻²)
C_{O_2}	Molar concentration of oxygen (mol·m ⁻³)
$D_{\text{O}_2}^{\text{eff}}$	Effective gas diffusion coefficient of oxygen (m ² ·s ⁻¹)

D_{i-j}^{eff}	Binary diffusion coefficient of species i and j ($\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$)
$D_{K,i}^{\text{eff}}$	Knudsen diffusion coefficient of species i ($\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$)
E_a	Activation energy of the charge transfer reaction ($\text{kJ} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$)
E^{tot}	Overall electrode potential (V)
F	Faraday constant ($\text{C} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$)
$F_{\text{inlet}}^{\text{tot}}$	Inlet flux for the gas channel ($\text{mol} \cdot \text{m}^{-2} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$)
$F_{\text{outlet}}^{\text{tot}}$	Outlet flux for the gas channel ($\text{mol} \cdot \text{m}^{-2} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$)
i_{el}	Electronic current density ($\text{A} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2}$)
i_{io}	Ionic current density ($\text{A} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2}$)
k_{00}	Pre-exponential factor of the kinetic constant ($\text{mol} \cdot \text{m}^{-1} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$)
k_{ct}	Global kinetic constant ($\text{mol} \cdot \text{m}^{-1} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$)
m	Reaction order (-)
m_i	Molar mass of the i th species ($\text{g} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$)
N_{O_2}	Molar flux of oxygen ($\text{mol} \cdot \text{m}^{-3} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$)
n	Number of moles of electrons (mol)
$P_{\text{O}_2, \text{in}}$	O_2 inlet partial pressure (atm)
P_{ref}	Reference O_2 pressure (atm)
\bar{r}_{pores}	Mean pore radius (m)
R	Ideal gas constant ($\text{J}/[\text{mol} \cdot \text{K}]$)
S_{O_2}	Mass source or sink of oxygen ($\text{mol} \cdot \text{m}^{-3} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$)
$\dot{S}_{\text{el}/\text{io}}$	Source or sink terms of the electronic and ionic charges ($\text{A} \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$)
S_p	Specific surface area (μm^{-1})
T	Operating temperature (K)
V_{cstr}	Volume of the CSTR (m^3)
V_i	Fuller volume of the i th species (-)
x	Molar fraction (-)
z	Local out-of-plane coordinate in the electrode bulk

Greek Symbols

α_{ox}	Oxidation transfer coefficient (-)
ε_i	Volume fraction of the i phase (-)
$\eta(z)$	Local electrode overvoltage (V)
η^{tot}	Overall electrode overvoltage (V)
λ_{TPB}	Length of triple-phase boundary sites per unit volume (μm^{-2})
$\tilde{\mu}_{e^-}$	Electrochemical potential of the electrons ($\text{J} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$)
$\tilde{\mu}_{\text{O}_2^{2-}}$	Electrochemical potential of the oxygen ions ($\text{J} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$)
σ^{eff}	Effective conductivity ($\text{S} \cdot \text{m}^{-1}$)
σ_{el}	Bulk electronic conductivity ($\text{S} \cdot \text{m}^{-1}$)
σ_{io}	Bulk ionic conductivity ($\text{S} \cdot \text{m}^{-1}$)
τ_i	Tortuosity factor of the i phase (-)
$\varphi_{\text{el}}(z)$	Local electronic potential in the Ni phase (V)
$\varphi_{\text{io}}(z)$	Local ionic potential in the YSZ phase (V)

Subscripts and Superscripts

act	Activation
ct	Charge-transfer
eff	Effective
el	Electronic
K	Knudsen
i, j	Species i, j
io	Ionic
pores	Porous phase
ref	Reference
B	Triple-phase boundary
tot	Total
SBCCO	$\text{SmBa}_{0.8}\text{Ca}_{0.2}\text{Co}_2\text{O}_{5+\delta}$
e^-	Electrons
O_2	Oxygen

1. Introduction

The excessive employment of carbon-based fuels such as coal, oil and gas, in the last 100 years has triggered the ongoing global energy crisis. CO₂ emissions originating from power generation burning fossil fuels are one of the key contributors to climate change and related environmental problems. Increasing energy demand and progressive depletion of fossil fuel reserves make power generation from fossils unsustainable. The development and global deployment of new energy conversion technologies are required and must be undertaken to respect the environmental regulations put in place to contain the effects of climate change. Within this framework, solid oxide cells (SOCs) are gaining interest due to their operational properties such as high efficiency, reversibility and fuel flexibility [1–4].

The architecture of the state-of-the-art SOCs includes a thin dense electrolyte ($\sim 8\text{--}10\ \mu\text{m}$) sandwiched between a thick supporting fuel electrode ($\sim 250\text{--}300\ \mu\text{m}$) and a thinner air electrode ($\sim 30\text{--}50\ \mu\text{m}$) [5]. The conventional electrolyte consists of zirconia doped with yttria (YSZ) [6] while the fuel electrode is usually a cermet composite of Ni and YSZ [7]. A mixed ionic and electronic conductor (MIEC), such as lanthanum strontium cobalt ferrite (LSCF), mixed with an ionic conductor such as gadolinium-doped ceria (CGO) [8], is classically used at the air electrode.

SOCs operate at high temperatures ($700\ ^\circ\text{C}\text{--}800\ ^\circ\text{C}$) to enable ionic conduction in the electrolyte and electro-catalytic activity within the electrodes. In conventional composite electrodes, the charge-transfer reaction takes place at the triple-phase boundary (TPB) sites where the electron-conducting, ion-conducting electrolyte and gas phases meet [9–11]. However, when an MIEC is used as a single electrode material, charge-transfer reaction can occur at the double-phase boundary (DPB). Therefore, in this case, since the MIEC conducts both ions and electrons throughout its bulk phase, the reaction can take place directly at the electrode-gas interface. The performance of SOCs is highly dependent on the electrocatalytic activity of the electrodes, and their efficiency is controlled both by their microstructural characteristics and intrinsic material properties [9, 12–21]. With regard to electrode materials, there are a number of general and specific requirements that they should fulfill to promote high electrochemical performance, durability and upscaling. Specifically, low cost, abundance, chemical and mechanical stability over time are all relevant aspects that must be sought to increase the capability of SOCs.

Several crystallographic structures have been proposed for air electrodes in recent years. Layered oxides have been extensively explored as promising oxygen electrode materials, being characterized by high ionic and electronic conductivities and remarkable electrochemical performance. In particular, among them layered barium cobaltites such as double perovskite oxides, referred to as $\text{LnBaCo}_2\text{O}_{5+\delta}$ ($\text{Ln} = \text{Sm, Pr, Nd, Gd and Y}$), have gained significant attention across various studies [22–25].

Despite their distinctive properties, substituting state-of-the-art materials with more novel alternatives such as $\text{LnBaCo}_2\text{O}_{5+\delta}$ necessitates a thorough comprehension of the material activity during operation [26]. To tackle this challenge, physics-based models stand as key tools to enable the investigation of the phenomena occurring in SOC electrodes. Concerning the electrode kinetics, the oxygen reduction and evolution reactions (ORR and OER, respectively) can be modeled as a sequence of coupled elementary sub-reactions at the atomic level, each having its own equilibrium and rate constants. Donazzi *et al* [27] and Effori *et al* [28] developed models based on an elementary description of the reaction pathway. When combined with the charged and mass transport conservations, they were used to simulate the dynamic responses of LSCF and LSCF-CGO air electrodes [26, 28–30]. Ascolani-Yael *et al* developed a phenomenological model to address the finite-length nature of air electrodes, where the reaction occurs across the total electrode thickness [31]. Since the kinetic steps of OER and ORR take place through multiple intermediate steps (e.g. adsorption/desorption, surface ionization, incorporation/excorporation, ionic transfer [28]), several works, based on physics-based models have also adopted an empirical approach to describe the elementary reaction pathway [26, 32–34]. Generally, the latter is used to merge the single kinetic processes in one or two relevant steps, which is able to effectively reproduce the electrode reactivity. The first dynamic model for MIEC electrodes was published by Adler *et al* [35] and showed that the dynamic response of an MIEC electrode can be represented with a Gerischer type impedance, producing the typical hedgehog-shaped curve in the Nyquist diagram.

Since physically based models can drive the understanding of the electrode response, they can be used to guide the understanding of the low-frequency resistive contribution of air electrodes. Indeed, the interpretation of its physical nature is still not univocal. Previous works showing electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) data of air electrode materials addressed the low-frequency resistance to poor mass transfer occurring within the diffusion channels. Indeed, the physical processes observed at low characteristic frequencies are commonly associated with adsorption/desorption and diffusion phenomena [36–39]. However, other studies highlighted the importance of (i) electrode microstructure, (ii) electrode performance and (iii) adopted operating conditions (gas flow rate, EIS parameters) towards the interpretation of the

low-frequency contributions. Specifically, the latter was also addressed to the gas conversion process [40] when the EIS data were taken/simulated at open-circuit voltage (OCV) and with finite gas supply [28, 41, 42].

While stationary and dynamic physically based models on LSCF and lanthanum strontium manganite (LSM) were developed in detail by different research groups [11, 27, 28, 43, 44], there are only a few on different air electrode materials. Nonetheless, many promising MIEC electrocatalysts showing high properties have been reported in the literature [15, 45–47] and stand as potential substitutes for LSCF and LSM, thus spurring on a deeper understanding of their electrochemical behavior. Furthermore, the interpretation of EIS contributions related to mass transport and gas conversion is mainly dependent on the microstructural properties of the electrode and the adopted operating conditions. Therefore, the results obtained on different materials can be extended to electrode architectures tested under similar operating conditions.

In light of the excellent properties shown by $\text{SmBa}_{0.8}\text{Ca}_{0.2}\text{Co}_2\text{O}_{5+\delta}$ (SBCCO), characterized by low polarization resistance compared to the state-of-the-art materials (e.g. LSM and LSCF, as reported in previous works [48, 49]), it is regarded that this material can hold the potential of improving the performance of current SOCs air electrodes. However, under certain operating conditions, its electrochemical response results are limited by the low-frequency contribution. In this context, this study aims to identify the nature of the latter, also due to the excellent electrochemical performance of SBCCO, which aids in evidencing its impact and revealing the remaining uncertainties on the physical phenomenon behind the process. Within this framework, for the first time to the best of the authors' knowledge, the electrochemical performance of SBCCO was taken as a reference for the calibration and validation of a tailored microstructure-resolved framework. Specifically, the impact of gas diffusion and gas conversion is analyzed in detail to highlight the nature of the limiting transport phenomena in the adopted operating conditions. In a broader context, the developed framework can be regarded as providing valuable insight into the physical mechanisms underlying the resistive contributions of general MIEC air electrode materials, holding a classic homogeneous microstructure.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Manufacturing and testing of SBCCO symmetrical cells

The description of the manufacturing process and electrochemical testing of SBCCO-based electrodes was previously detailed in [49], thus only the main characteristics are dealt with below. The synthesis of the SBCCO powders was carried out following a modified Pechini method, as detailed in [19]. The obtained SBCCO powders were calcined and subsequently screen-printed onto electrolyte-supported cells composed of pressed and sintered pellets of $\text{Sm}_{0.2}\text{Ce}_{0.8}\text{O}_{2-\delta}$ (SDC) from FuelCellMaterials. This process shaped button cells holding a symmetrical configuration of SBCCO/SDC/SBCCO, with an active area of $\sim 0.3\text{ cm}^2$. The EIS measurements and $I-\eta$ characteristics of the fabricated SBCCO/SDC/SBCCO symmetrical cells were carried out in the temperature range $650\text{ }^\circ\text{C}-750\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, at different partial pressures with a $60\text{ Nml}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ inlet flow rate, using commercial Probostat test stations (NOR-ECS, Norway). The impedance measurements were recorded in the $1\text{ MHz}-0.01\text{ Hz}$ frequency range with a 20 mV perturbation amplitude. The analysis of the EIS results was also supported by the use of an in-house distribution of relaxation times (DRTs) tool to aid the interpretation of the main resistive mechanisms [50].

2.2. Morphological characterization: SEM analysis and 3D reconstruction

The microstructural analysis obtained from the observation of the field-emission scanning electron microscope (FE-SEM, AURIGA with Gemini 30 kV FE-SEM column from ZEISS) images was supported by the use of a mathematical tool based on the Gaussian random field method [51]. For the experimental characterization, the samples were embedded in a two-component epoxy resin to reinforce the porous microstructure, providing added stability during SEM imaging and enabling more precise planar sectioning. This embedding process is crucial for identifying the pore phase in image processing since the resin fills the pores and appears as dark black in contrast to the light gray electrode material, enhancing the visibility of structural details. The mathematical model is then used to reproduce the 3D microstructure of a two-phase (solid-gas, 2P) architecture, i.e. the experimental SBCCO-porous electrode. It can be pointed out that the investigation of the electrode properties could be performed by the use of experimental 3D characterization methods, such as focused ion beam-SEM (FIB-SEM) or nano-holotomography, as also previously reported in [16, 28, 29, 52]. However, as (i) the RF model is validated on real electrode microstructures, thus ensuring its representativeness, (ii) the electrodes are manufactured by screen printing, hence yielding a homogeneous microstructure, and (iii) since experimental 3D characterization methods are not always easily accessible, we propose a combination of SEM micrographs with numerical modeling to extract the electrode properties.

The model description and its validation on classical SOC porous electrodes were previously analyzed in detail in [51, 53]; thus, only its main features are reported hereafter.

The RF model shapes SOC electrode microstructures by the generation of a Gaussian random noise, which is correlated to a weight function. This encompasses the geostatistical information linked to the emulated stochastic microstructure. In particular, the model generates a stationary and normal centered random Gaussian field, which holds the same spatial correlations as the real microstructure (described by the weight function). The virtual microstructure for a 2P electrode can be built either by reproducing the solid or gas phase because no considerable differences were found from the typical tested electrodes [51]. The stochastic nature of the framework also leads to the generation of different microstructures at any realization. However, the latter shows the same characteristics if considering a volume large enough to be statistically representative (i.e. $\sim 12^3 \mu\text{m}^3$). The fields are then thresholded to obtain a synthetic volume with the same average properties as the targeted microstructure. It must also be emphasized that an important advantage of this method is its fast execution time compared to the more classical sphere packing algorithms [54–56] since it does not require any iteration. Finally, it can be remarked that the representativeness of the virtual microstructures shaped by the RF model is guaranteed by the limited error percentage measured between the characteristics of real and calibrated RF electrodes, as detailed in [51].

For the purpose of this study, the mean phase diameter and volume fraction of the porous and solid phases (d_{pores} , $\varepsilon_{\text{pores}}$, d_{SBCCO} , $\varepsilon_{\text{SBCCO}}$, respectively) were extracted from the 2D SEM images and used as inputs for the RF model. The latter generated the synthetic reconstruction of a 2P electrode holding the microstructural properties retrieved from the experimental SBCCO architecture.

2.3. Model description

The electrochemical behavior of an MIEC air electrode is simulated in this study by a physics-based model, which captures the relevant transport and reaction phenomena occurring within the electrode. A framework is developed based on an equivalent homogeneous medium, reproducing an isothermal slice of a porous SBCCO electrode including a portion of the SDC electrolyte (figure 1). The effective properties used in the physics-based model are computed from the 3D reconstruction of the electrode obtained from the RF framework and are expressed through its characteristic microstructural properties. A model was developed to simulate the electrode response for both stationary and dynamic behaviors in the vicinity of the OCV. The reaction mechanism, mass and charge transport equations are implemented in the model to reproduce the experimental electrochemical performance of SBCCO electrodes.

2.3.1. Reaction mechanism

A simplified reaction mechanism is adopted in this study to simulate the electrochemical performance of an MIEC air electrode material. The detailed reaction mechanisms of state-of-the-art architectures, such as LSCF and LSCF-CGO, were previously reported in [27, 28] and were expressed as a sequence of elementary reactions. The development of micro-kinetic models can effectively describe the microscopic processes that take place in the active layer for the OER and ORR. However, their validation requires a detailed knowledge

of the simulated material properties (e.g. concentration of vacancies at equilibrium, the available number of active sites on the electrode surface, and species diffusivities [28]), which is still to be acquired for novel air electrode materials such as SBCCO. Therefore, a single charge-transfer reaction, taking place at the surface SBCCO/porosity, was used to simulate the global redox reaction (equation (1)):

where $\text{V}_{\text{O}}^{\cdot}(\text{SBCCO})$ refers to the oxygen vacancies within the bulk of SBCCO. The proposed, as well documented in the literature [57–59], kinetic rate of the charge-transfer reactions follows a phenomenological approach stemming from the Butler–Volmer formalism (equation (2)):

$$\nu(z) = S_p^{\text{SBCCO/air}} \cdot k_{\text{ct}} \cdot \left[e^{\frac{2\alpha_{\text{ox}}F\eta(z)}{RT}} - \left(\frac{P_{\text{O}_2}(z)}{P_{\text{ref}}} \right) \cdot e^{\frac{-2\alpha_{\text{red}}F\eta(z)}{RT}} \right], \quad (2)$$

where $\nu(z)$ is the kinetic rate ($\text{mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}\text{s}^{-1}$) evaluated across the electrode thickness, k_{ct} is the proposed global kinetic constant for the forward and reverse charge-transfer reactions ($\text{mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$), $P_{\text{O}_2}(z)$ is the local oxygen partial pressure (-), P_{ref} is the reference gas pressure (atm), α_{ox} is the oxidation transfer coefficient and α_{red} is the reduction transfer coefficient (with $\alpha_{\text{ox}} + \alpha_{\text{red}} = 1$), F , R and T are Faraday's constant ($\text{C}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$), the universal gas constant ($\text{J}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$) and the operating temperature (K), respectively. The dependency of the kinetic rate on the characteristic electrode microstructural properties is outlined in terms of the direct dependency of $\nu(z)$ from $S_p^{\text{SBCCO/air}}$ (m^{-1}), i.e. the specific surface area between SBCCO and air where the charge-transfer reaction is assumed to take place. The proposed expression for the global kinetic constant is reported in equation (3):

$$k_{\text{ct}} = k_{00} \cdot \left(\frac{P_{\text{O}_2,\text{in}}}{P_{\text{ref}}} \right)^m \cdot e^{\frac{-E_a}{RT}}, \quad (3)$$

where k_{00} ($\text{mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$) is the pre-exponential factor, m is a constant coefficient (-), E_a is the activation energy of the reaction (kJ/mol) and $P_{\text{O}_2,\text{in}}$ is the inlet oxygen partial pressure (atm). It can be remarked that the charge-transfer reaction was not simulated at the TPB sites, located at the interface SBCCO/SDC. The latter assumption is derived from the investigated electrode architecture, which contains only the SBCCO solid phase screen-printed over the SDC pellet, thus minimizing the number of TPB sites compared to composite microstructures.

In the model, the local overpotential within the electrode $\eta(z)$ (V) is expressed as the difference between the local electronic potential (φ_{el}) and the local ionic potential (φ_{io}) in SBCCO, equation (4),

$$\eta(z) = \varphi_{\text{el}}(z) - \varphi_{\text{io}}(z) = \frac{\tilde{\mu}_{\text{e}^-}}{F} + \frac{\tilde{\mu}_{\text{O}_2^-}}{2F}, \quad (4)$$

where $\tilde{\mu}_{\text{e}^-}$ and $\tilde{\mu}_{\text{O}_2^-}$ express the electrochemical potentials of the electrons and oxygen ions.

2.3.2. Mass and charge transport for the model species

The dusty gas model (DGM) is used to describe the diffusion of gases, while the electronic and ionic currents are computed considering classical Ohm's law [60, 61]. For the gas species, the mass balances and the equations which express the diffusive flux are equations (5) and (6):

$$\varepsilon_{\text{pores}} \frac{dC_{\text{O}_2}}{dt} = -\nabla \cdot N_{\text{O}_2} \pm S_{\text{O}_2}, \quad (5)$$

$$N_{\text{O}_2} = -D_{\text{O}_2}^{\text{eff}} \nabla C_{\text{O}_2}, \quad (6)$$

where $\varepsilon_{\text{pores}}$ is the pore volume fraction in the electrode while C_{O_2} and N_{O_2} are the molar concentration ($\text{mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) and flux ($\text{mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$) of oxygen, S_{O_2} represents the source/sink term associated with the reactions in which O_2 is produced/consumed ($\text{mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$) and $D_{\text{O}_2}^{\text{eff}}$ is the effective O_2 gas diffusion coefficient ($\text{m}^2\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$).

The effective diffusion coefficient is derived from the DGM, following the approach reported in [61–63]. This last approximation is especially relevant for the microstructure of typical SOC air electrodes in which the mass transfer is assumed to be fully limited by the gas diffusion process [64]. Under this condition, the effective coefficient $D_{\text{O}_2}^{\text{eff}}$, given in equation (6), is obtained from the combination of the binary (D_{i-j}^{eff}) and

Knudsen diffusion coefficients ($D_{K,i}^{\text{eff}}$). The first is expressed according to Fuller's theory in equation (7) while the second depends on the mean pore radius (\bar{r}_{pores}), equation (8):

$$D_{i-j}^{\text{eff}} = \frac{\varepsilon_{\text{pores}}}{\tau_{\text{pores}}} \cdot \frac{0.00143}{P_{\text{tot}} (\sqrt[3]{V_i} + \sqrt[3]{V_j})^2 \sqrt{\frac{2}{\frac{1}{M_i} + \frac{1}{M_j}}}} \cdot T^{1.75} \cdot 10^{-4}, \quad (7)$$

$$D_{K,i} = \frac{\varepsilon_{\text{pores}}}{\tau_{\text{pores}}} \cdot \bar{r}_{\text{pores}} \cdot \frac{2}{3} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{8 \cdot 1000 \cdot RT}{\pi M_i}}, \quad (8)$$

where τ_{pores} is the apparent tortuosity factor for the gas phase, M_i is the molar mass of the i th species expressed in $\text{g}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ and V_i is the Fuller volume of the i th species (O_2 and N_2) taken from [65].

The electronic and ionic current densities of the electrodes are reported in equations (9) and (10), together with the corresponding effective conductivities:

$$i_{\text{el}} = -\sigma_{\text{el}}^{\text{eff}} \nabla \varphi_{\text{el}} \sigma_{\text{el}}^{\text{eff}} = \frac{\varepsilon_{\text{el}}}{\tau_{\text{el}}} \sigma_{\text{el}}, \quad (9)$$

$$i_{\text{io}} = -\sigma_{\text{io}}^{\text{eff}} \nabla \varphi_{\text{io}} \sigma_{\text{io}}^{\text{eff}} = \frac{\varepsilon_{\text{io}}}{\tau_{\text{io}}} \sigma_{\text{io}}, \quad (10)$$

where σ_{el} and σ_{io} are the bulk electronic and ionic conductivities of SBCCO. It should be emphasized that all the diffusivities and conductivities can be expressed as a function of the electrode microstructural properties taking into account the effect of the electrode microstructure on the mass/charge transport phenomena. Only the effective ionic conductivity of the SDC used for the electrolyte was taken as a property of the dense material (i.e. $\varepsilon_{\text{io,electrolyte}} = 1$, $\tau_{\text{io,electrolyte}} = 1$). It should also be remarked that the description of the oxygen-ion transfer resistance at the electrode/electrolyte interface was not taken into account in the model. Indeed, especially at high operating temperature, its resistive contribution was found to be negligible compared to the high-frequency response of SOC air electrodes [26, 35, 66]. Furthermore, the focus of the electrochemical investigation is on the physical nature of the low-frequency contributions, while the ionic transfer step can only be evidenced at very high frequencies ($>10^4$ Hz [26, 28, 35, 66]), thus being beyond the main scope of this study.

The charge conservation equations for the electronic and ionic conductive phases are reported in equations (11) and (12), respectively:

$$+S_p^{\text{SBCCO/air}} C_{\text{ct}} \frac{dE}{dt} = -\nabla \cdot \vec{i}_{\text{el}} \pm \dot{S}_{\text{el}}, \quad (11)$$

$$-S_p^{\text{SBCCO/air}} C_{\text{ct}} \frac{dE}{dt} = -\nabla \cdot \vec{i}_{\text{io}} \pm \dot{S}_{\text{io}}, \quad (12)$$

where C_{ct} is the charge-transfer capacitance taking into account the global capacitive effects at the reaction surface ($\text{F}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$) and $\pm \dot{S}_{\text{el/io}}$ are the source/sink terms of the electronic and ionic charges ($\text{A}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$) according to the operating mode, which are related to the kinetics rate of the charge-transfer reactions via equation (13):

$$\dot{S}_{\text{el/io}} = nF\nu. \quad (13)$$

It must be noted that a positive flux of charges is associated with a negative current, meaning that the reaction is considered as a sink if it produces charged species, and vice versa. Within the bulk of the electrolyte phase, the ionic current is not associated with any reaction and no capacitance effect arises from the accumulation of charges due to the absence of the interface with the electronic conducting material, thus meaning $\nabla \cdot \vec{i}_{\text{io}} = 0$.

Finally, the impact of gas conversion on the EIS diagrams was evaluated. Specifically, the model details the evolution of the electrode dynamic response driven by the impact of gas transport. The gas conversion contribution to the impedance spectra arises from the consumption and production of species that modify the gas composition in the channels distributing the gas over the electrode [67]. In order to consider this contribution in the EIS data, the channels are modeled as continuous stirred tank reactors (CSTRs) [28, 40–42]. The CSTR model allows us to compute the boundary conditions in terms of gas partial pressures that must be applied at the top of the electrode. The inlet and outlet fluxes are linked according to the mass balance shown by equation (14) [28, 67]:

$$\frac{P_{\text{tot}} V_{\text{cstr}}}{RT} \frac{dx_{\text{O}_2}(z=0)}{dt} = F_{\text{inlet}}^{\text{tot}} x_{\text{O}_2}^{\text{inlet}}(t, z=0) - F_{\text{outlet}}^{\text{tot}} x_{\text{O}_2}(t, z=0) \pm |N_{\text{O}_2}(t, z=0)| \times A_{\text{electrode}}, \quad (14)$$

where $\pm |N_{O_2}(t, z = 0)|$ is the oxygen flux taken at the top of the electrode, depending on the operating mode, V_{cstr} represents the volume of the CSTR, the terms F_{inlet}^{tot} and F_{outlet}^{tot} denote the inlet and outlet fluxes for the gas channel, respectively, and $A_{electrode}$ is the electrode surface area. It must be highlighted that modeling the gas channels as CSTRs is legitimate only when the concentration overpotentials are limited, and thus when the electrode is tested in the vicinity of the OCV [28, 42]. Otherwise, a 2D model description constituted by a series of electrode slices would be required to account for the oxygen partial pressure evolution along the electrode length [41].

2.3.3. Boundary conditions and input parameters

The equations of charge/mass balances combined with the expressions of fluxes and source terms constitute a set of partial differential equations implemented in the software for finite-element computation Comsol Multiphysics® and solved for stationary and dynamic models.

In both models, the overall electrode overpotential is taken as the difference between the electric potential at the CC/FL interface ($z = 0$) and the ionic potential at the FL/EL interface ($z = l_{fl}$), as shown in equation (15):

$$\eta^{tot} = \varphi_{el}(z = 0) - \varphi_{io}(z = l_{fl}). \quad (15)$$

The simulation of the impedance spectra was carried out in accordance with the procedure reported by Hubert *et al* [68]. A sinusoidal perturbation was applied at each frequency, imposing the ionic current in the electrolyte as:

$$i_{io,EL}(z = l_{fl} + l_{el}, t) = i_{io,DC} + i_{io,AC} \cdot \sin(2\pi ft). \quad (16)$$

The models were run using a perturbation amplitude $i_{io,AC} = 5 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$ in the frequency range between 10^{-2} and 10^6 Hz calculating ten points per decade of frequency. In this study, due to the limited extension of the investigated current density, only spectra at OCV were simulated.

The imposed boundary conditions are:

- (i) For the electronic phase (i.e. SBCCO):

$$\varphi_{el}(z = 0) = 0,$$

$$i_{el}(z = l_{fl}) = 0.$$

- (ii) For the ionic phase (i.e. SBCCO):

$$i_{io}(z = 0) = 0,$$

$$i_{io}(z = l_{fl} + l_{el}) = \text{imposed}.$$

- (iii) For the gas phase (i.e. porosity):

$$C_{O_2}(z = 0) = \text{imposed},$$

$$N_{O_2}(z = l_{fl}) = 0.$$

Regarding the input parameters for the simulations, all the microstructural properties were extracted from the synthetic volume obtained from the RF model. The effective gas diffusivities were calculated from the combination of equations (7) and (8) while the bulk ionic and electronic conductivity of SBCCO were estimated from [69] and [70], respectively. Table 1 reports the values of the diffusion coefficients and conductivities, which were used as input parameters at different operating temperatures.

Table 1. List of diffusion coefficients and conductivities used in the electrochemical model. D_{K,O_2} and D_{K,N_2} are reported as normalized values [28].

	650 °C	700 °C	750 °C	Units
$D_{O_2-N_2}$	1.04×10^{-4}	1.40×10^{-4}	1.80×10^{-4}	$(m^2 \cdot s^{-1})$
D_{K,O_2}	468.72	508.34	546.58	$(m \cdot s^{-1})$
D_{K,N_2}	521.04	571.73	586.21	$(m \cdot s^{-1})$
$\sigma_{el,SBCCO}$	5.08×10^4 ([70])	3.98×10^4 ([70])	3.16×10^4 ([70])	$(S \cdot m^{-1})$
$\sigma_{io,SBCCO}$	7.94 ([69])	11.58 ([69])	15.84 ([69])	$(S \cdot m^{-1})$

Figure 2. (a) SEM micrograph of the polished cross-section of the SBCCO electrode; (b) segmented cross-section of the electrode; (c) 3D image of RVE derived from the RF model, tailored on the characteristics of the screen-printed SBCCO electrodes.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Microstructural properties

The SEM micrographs reported in figures 2(a) and (b) show the original and segmented cross-sections of the manufactured SBCCO electrode, screen-printed over a thick SDC pellet. The SBCCO electrode microstructure exhibits a typical sponge-like porosity characterized by the presence of fine pores homogeneously distributed in the layer. Statistical investigations over the electrode microstructure were performed by analyzing multiple SEM micrographs using the software IMAGEJ and previously validated computational scripts, with the purpose of characterizing the mean phase diameter of porosity and the volume fractions of the two phases. The procedure used for the segmentation of the images and the statistical analyses of the microstructure characteristics adopts the processing steps previously reported in [29]. Specifically, the electrode phases can be identified by their corresponding gray levels in the SEM micrographs (darker: pores, gray: SBCCO, figure 2(a)). Before computing the electrode microstructural properties, the images were segmented by labeling the SBCCO and pore phases. The micrographs were also filtered by in-house codes to increase the contrast between the SBCCO and porosity and deconvolute the peaks in the histogram. The filtering is based on the Malik–Perona method [71] and the procedure followed in this study is reported in [69]. Subsequently, each of the two phases of the electrode were labelled univocally using the threshold identified by Otsu’s approach (found to be equal to 110) [72]. The segmentation procedure was followed by the extraction of the average electrode properties through the computational methods previously detailed in [9, 29, 68, 73]. Specifically, the average d_{pores} were ~ 820 nm, while ε_{pores} and ε_{SBCCO} were estimated to be ~ 0.38 and ~ 0.62 , respectively. As introduced in section 2.2, the extracted ε_{pores} , d_{pores} and ε_{SBCCO} were used as inputs of the RF framework, for the generation of a 3D reconstruction tailored to the experimental SBCCO electrode. Figure 2(c) shows the estimated 3D image of the SBCCO electrode, which is characterized by a cube edge size of $15 \mu m$. Specifically, in order to measure the average microstructural properties of a homogeneous screen-printed electrode, it is necessary to analyze a volume sufficiently large to be statistically representative of the investigated characteristics. This volume is usually referred to as the representative volume element (RVE) and its identification can be obtained by varying the edge size (l) of cubic subdomains and calculating the standard deviation of different microstructural properties as a function of l . The procedure for the identification of the RVE of classical homogeneous electrodes was previously detailed in [30] and showed that a cube edge size of $15 \mu m$ is sufficiently large to be statistically representative. Therefore, being a screen-printed SBCCO electrode characterized by homogeneous properties, an RVE of $15^3 \mu m^3$ was selected as a representative sub-volume for the entire microstructure.

From the 3D images, the volume fraction of each phase was extracted as well as the pore size, the tortuosity factor and $S_p^{SBCCO/air}$, to be later implemented within the 1D electrochemical model. Due to its

Table 2. Microstructural bulk properties of the SBCCO electrode.

Properties of the connected phases		
Pore volume fraction ($\varepsilon_{\text{pores}}$)	0.38	(—)
SBCCO volume fraction ($\varepsilon_{\text{SBCCO}}$)	0.62	(—)
Mean pore radius (\bar{r}_{pores})	0.41	(μm)
Mean SBCCO radius (\bar{r}_{SBCCO})	0.56	(μm)
Specific surface area ($S_p^{\text{SBCCO/air}}$)	0.96	(μm^{-1})
Pores tortuosity factor (τ_{pores})	2.47	(—)
SBCCO tortuosity factor (τ_{SBCCO})	1.56	(—)

Table 3. Best-fitting kinetic parameters used for the 1D electrochemical simulations.

Calibrated kinetic parameters		
k_{00}	2.73×10^5	$\text{mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$
E_a	151.8	$\text{kJ}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$
m	0.6	—
$\alpha_{\text{ox}}, \alpha_{\text{red}}$	0.5	—

intrinsic microstructural homogeneity, the properties of the traditional electrode architecture were computed as bulk properties, thus measuring the average characteristics of the RVE volume (table 2). The distribution of the pore size is also reported in the supplementary material.

3.2. Electrochemical simulations

3.2.1. Model calibration and validation

The proposed 1D physics-based model is calibrated on the experimental data of the SBCCO electrode previously reported in [48, 49]. The fitting procedure was performed on the reference $I-\eta$ curves targeting the error minimization between the reference data and the simulated ones to enable the determination of a single set of solutions for the missing kinetic parameters. The experimental $I-\eta$ curves were fitted in the current density range -0.1 to $0.1 \text{ A}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$, at three different operating temperatures ($650 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $700 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $750 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) and inlet gas partial pressures ($P_{\text{O}_2,\text{in}}/P_{\text{N}_2,\text{in}} = 10/90, 21/79$ and $100/0$ respectively). The extraction of k_{ct} was obtained following an iterative procedure while E_a and k_{00} were estimated plotting $\ln(k_{\text{ct}})$ versus $1000/T$, thus retrieving E_a from the slope of the resulting linear curve and k_{00} as the intercept of the y axis. It should be noted that a single E_a value was extracted for both the fuel cell and electrolysis operating modes due to the limited extension of the investigated current range. The different slopes of the solid oxide fuel cell (SOFC) and solid oxide electrolyzer cell (SOEC) operating modes could, instead, be markedly observed at larger current densities, thus potentially requiring more complex reaction rates depending on the forward and backward kinetic constants [29, 30, 33]. The exponent m was extracted from the slope of the linear curve obtained when plotting $\log(k_{\text{ct}})$ versus $\log(P_{\text{O}_2})$, after following an iterative procedure to calibrate k_{ct} values at $750 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in the $0.1-1 P_{\text{O}_2,\text{in}}$ range. The values of the resulting best-fitting kinetic parameters are given in table 3. The calibrated kinetic parameters were used to reproduce the $I-\eta$ characteristics of a homogeneous SBCCO air electrode under the investigated experimental conditions. In other words, the same set of adjusted kinetic parameters was maintained to simulate the response of an SBCCO electrode in a range of plausible operating conditions, sweeping temperature and $P_{\text{O}_2,\text{in}}$ in the range $650 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}-750 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $0.1-1 \text{ atm } P_{\text{O}_2,\text{in}}$, respectively. The results of the fitting process at the three operating temperatures under $P_{\text{O}_2,\text{in}} = 0.21 \text{ atm}$ are reported in figure 3(a), while the fitting obtained sweeping $P_{\text{O}_2,\text{in}}$ at $T = 750 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ is shown in figure 3(b).

It is observed that the calibrated homogeneous model is able to accurately reproduce the shape of the experimental $I-\eta$ characteristics at each operating temperature and $P_{\text{O}_2,\text{in}}$. The simulated curves well predict the evolution of the experimental ones where the area-specific resistance decreases when the temperature and $P_{\text{O}_2,\text{in}}$ increase. The original and synthetic data showed a maximum mismatch of 5% at $650 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, thus highlighting the predictive capability of the developed framework. Furthermore, unlike experimental electrochemical characterization methods, the developed stationary model can provide valuable insight into the evolution of both ionic/electronic current densities and potentials across the electrode thickness. In experimental $I-\eta$ curves or EIS data, the values of η^{to} and i are measured on metallic grids placed over the surface of the electrodes, thus not providing any information on their distribution across the cell. The evolution of the electrode potential under polarization can instead be reproduced by micro-kinetic models such as the one presented in this study for SBCCO. Figures 4(a)–(d) report $\varphi_{\text{el}}(z)$, $\varphi_{\text{io}}(z)$, $i_{\text{el}}(z)$ and $i_{\text{io}}(z)$ at $750 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $P_{\text{O}_2,\text{in}} = 0.21 \text{ atm}$, in the current density range -0.1 to $0.1 \text{ A}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$.

Figures 4(a) and (b) show that the simulated results are consistent with the charge conservation equations (equations (11) and (12)) since the sum of i_{el} and i_{io} at any z coordinate is equal to the imposed current density. It can also be observed that the variation of the local potential within the electrode is mainly driven by the variation of $\varphi_{io}(z)$, as a gap of $\sim 10^3$ is obtained between the values of $\varphi_{el}(z)$ and $\varphi_{io}(z)$ (figures 4(c) and (d)). This difference stems from the higher value of $\sigma_{el,SBCCO}$ compared to $\sigma_{io,SBCCO}$, with the latter limiting the transport of charged species as in conventional SOC air electrode materials [27, 33, 74, 75]. Therefore, the relationship between $\varphi_{el,io}(z)$ and $i_{el,io}(z)$ expressed by equations (9) and (10) drives the evolution of $\varphi_{io}(z)$ and makes the variation of $\varphi_{el}(z)$ negligible.

Good accordance with simulated and experimental data under stationary operation was used to evaluate the predictive capability of the model in terms of electrode dynamic behavior. Specifically, to validate the

Figure 5. (a)–(c) Experimental and simulated Nyquist plots obtained from the EL model at 650 °C, 700 °C and 750 °C in air; (d), (e) and (f) corresponding DRT spectra obtained for the experimental and simulated data from the EL model at 650 °C, 700 °C and 750 °C in air.

simplified 1D framework, impedance diagrams were subsequently computed using the same kinetic parameters retrieved from the calibration of the stationary 1D model. The simulated dynamic response of SBCCO used to predict the shape of the experimental EIS data was computed devoting particular attention to the effect of gas conversion, expressed in equation (14). Specifically, two different time-dependent models were built starting from the stationary framework calibrated on the $I-\eta$ characteristics. Model EL was developed considering only the physical mechanisms taking place in the electrode domain, i.e. species transport and reaction phenomena (i.e. without equation (14) for gas conversion). Model GC, instead, extended the investigation to the gas channel feeding the reactants to the electrode, thus evaluating the contribution provided by the change in the gas composition linked to the EIS current perturbation.

3.2.1.1. Simulated EIS data—EL model

Figures 5(a)–(c) show the simulated EIS spectra in the 650 °C–750 °C range at $P_{\text{O}_2, \text{in}} = 0.21$ atm, obtained when neglecting the contribution of gas conversion, thus only considering the kinetic rate and transport phenomena occurring inside the electrode. Figures 5(d)–(f) show the corresponding DRT spectra, which were plotted using an in-house-developed procedure, namely extended domain DRTs (ED-DRT) [50]. Specifically, the DRT approach is regarded as providing deeper insight into the interpretation of the EIS data by performing deconvolution of the main resistive contributions and the identification of their characteristic relaxation times. For the purposes of this study, the ED-DRT procedure was integrated into the EIS data to evaluate the accordance with the characteristic frequencies of the experimental and simulated resistive peaks.

The simulated EIS responses in the Nyquist plots at 750 °C show that the simulated data hold the characteristic hedgehog shape, typical of Gerischer behavior, with a 45° slope followed by a final semi-circle [26, 76, 77]. The results obtained from the 1D framework are consistent with the Gerischer response of the ALS model for MIEC materials [35, 66]. As well documented in the literature, the Gerischer response can be interpreted as the result of the resistance originated by the combination of charge transport and ORR/OER kinetics, thus being consistent with the physical phenomena described by the EL model. At 650 °C, it can also be observed that the hedgehog shape displays a 45° slope followed by a more pronounced semi-circle. The shape of this Nyquist plot is a clear indication of finite-length Gerischer behavior with limiting kinetics, induced by the lower operating temperature [78–80]. It can be observed that the global polarization resistances (R_p) of the resulting simulated data well match those obtained experimentally, as was expected from the good fitting of the $I-\eta$ curves. However, it must be noted that the global reaction pathway of an MIEC air electrode is composed by a sequence of intermediate reactions whose complexity cannot be entirely reproduced by an electrochemical model based on an apparent single charge-transfer mechanism [29]. Modeling the electrode kinetics via fully elementary description is expected to improve the predictability and accuracy of the physical frameworks. However, as introduced in section 2.3, the validation of complex

Figure 6. (a), (b) and (c) Experimental and simulated Nyquist plots obtained from the EL model at 750 °C with $P_{O_2, in} = 0.1$ atm, $P_{O_2, in} = 0.21$ atm and $P_{O_2, in} = 1$ atm, respectively; (d), (e) and (f) corresponding DRT spectra obtained for the experimental and simulated data from the EL model at 750 °C with $P_{O_2, in} = 0.1$ atm, $P_{O_2, in} = 0.21$ atm and $P_{O_2, in} = 1$ atm.

micro-kinetic frameworks relies both on the accurate description of the electrode microstructural properties and the inherent materials' characteristics. Effori *et al* [28] developed a fully-elementary model for LSCF and LSCF-CGO air electrodes, simulating bulk and surface path for the oxygen transfer, thus including pure elementary steps involving neutral oxygen atoms, adsorbed ions and molecules. Parameters, such as the density of available sites on the LSCF surface, the concentration of oxygen vacancies or the oxygen vacancy self-diffusivity, were used as input properties, which were extracted from previous studies or experimental analyses [28, 81]. Furthermore, several parameters, such as the diffusion coefficients of the adsorbed species, the LSCF surface coverage at equilibrium and all the kinetic constants of the elementary steps, were estimated from the performed simulations, which were not retrieved from experimental measurements. Since SBCCO is a relatively novel air electrode material compared to the state-of-the-art LSM and LSCF, only a few studies and experimental investigations on its properties can be found in the literature [72, 82, 83]. However, the very promising electrochemical performance of SBCCO spurs on the development of detailed electrochemical investigations on this material. In this context, the single-step kinetic rate used in the adopted physical framework aims at reducing the uncertainties that could arise from the large number of unknown parameters. Nonetheless, its simplified structure targets the interpretation of the SBCCO electrochemical behavior and the extraction of global kinetic parameters validated on real microstructural properties. However, due to the implementation of a global charge-transfer rate, the complex shape of the experimental SBCCO Nyquist plots cannot be entirely captured by the model, as shown in figure 5. As an example, the resistive shoulder at high frequencies, which can be observed at 650 °C and 700 °C in the experimental DRT spectra, is not reproduced by the physical model. This resistive contribution, which was reported to be thermally activated and ascribed to the O^{2-} transfer at the electrolyte–electrode interface, can arise from the different ion-transport properties of SBCCO and SDC or from the imperfect adhesion of the electrode to the supporting electrolyte pellet [48, 49]. Nonetheless, the physical model focuses on the processes occurring between the solid and porous phases in the electrode bulk, thus not including any equation that could consider the O^{2-} transfer between SBCCO and SDC. However, it should also be pointed out that the framework can be easily adapted to describe this mechanism through the addition of a second reaction of ionic transfer, as reported in [28]. Furthermore, its impact will be accurately detailed in upcoming studies dealing with SBCCO-based composite electrodes.

The same approach followed for the simulation of EIS data at different operating temperatures was maintained to predict the dynamic electrode behavior sweeping $P_{O_2, in}$ in the 0.1–1 atm range. The simulated Nyquist plots and corresponding DRT spectra obtained at $P_{O_2, in} = 0.1$ atm, $P_{O_2, in} = 0.21$ atm and $P_{O_2, in} = 1$ atm are reported in figure 6, respectively.

The simulations at different operating temperatures, as well as the Nyquist plots obtained when sweeping $P_{O_2, in}$, show the characteristic hedgehog shape typical of MIEC air electrode materials. It must be noted that when $P_{O_2, in} = 0.1$ atm, the electrode performance starts to be limited by its kinetics as hinted by the

Table 4. Calibrated values for C_{ct} under the investigated operating conditions.

Temperature/ P_{O_2}	C_{ct}	Unit
650 °C/ $P_{O_2,in} = 0.21$ atm	3.52	$F \cdot m^{-2}$
700 °C/ $P_{O_2,in} = 0.21$ atm	2.07	$F \cdot m^{-2}$
750 °C/ $P_{O_2,in} = 0.21$ atm	4.51	$F \cdot m^{-2}$
750 °C/ $P_{O_2,in} = 0.1$ atm	8.67	$F \cdot m^{-2}$
750 °C/ $P_{O_2,in} = 1$ atm	9.81	$F \cdot m^{-2}$

finite-length Gerischer shape. Therefore, the shape of all the simulated Nyquist plots does not well reproduce the one of the experimental data. Nevertheless, the DRT spectra highlight that the characteristic frequencies of the main resistive contribution (HF) at different operating temperatures and oxygen partial pressures can be well captured by the EL model. This result was obtained by the calibration of C_{ct} , i.e. the global charge-transfer capacitance is assumed to take into account all the double-layer effects arising from the ORR/OER reaction. The fitted values of C_{ct} are reported in table 4.

The analysis of the experimental EIS data reported both in figures 5 and 6 highlights the presence of a low-frequency (LF) resistive peak, which appears as a small semicircle in the Nyquist plot and as a minor resistive peak in the DRT spectra. It must be noted that the relevance of the LF peak on the global R_p of the electrode increases at higher operating temperature and lower $P_{O_2,in}$, respectively. In previous works studying the EIS spectra of air electrode materials, the LF contribution was attributed to the poor mass transfer within the electrode diffusion channels. Indeed, the processes observed at low characteristic frequencies are commonly associated with adsorption/desorption and diffusion phenomena [36–39]. However, the simulated impedance diagrams, which have been obtained correlating the specific microstructural properties of the electrode to its electrochemical behavior, never highlight this resistive contribution. In other words, the estimated bulk values of ε_{pores} and τ_{pores} and \bar{r}_{pores} were found to be consistent with those reported for screen-printed or tape-cast electrodes [9, 33, 42, 52, 84–87], thus not limiting the mass transfer in the gas diffusion channels. As a result, none of the simulated EIS data highlight a low-frequency resistive contribution while showing the performance co-limitation arising from charge transport and reaction mechanisms.

In order to look into the impact of the microstructural properties on the resulting D_i^{eff} values (i.e. in the gas diffusion process), a sensitivity analysis was performed sweeping D_i^{eff} to lower values (figure 7). Specifically, the latter is aimed at capturing the evolution of the dynamic response of MIEC electrodes, considering only the impact of gas diffusion. The main purpose of this approach is the identification of potential microstructural properties, which can lead to performance limitations arising from gas diffusion, thus correlating the electrode microstructure and its electrochemical response. Furthermore, the evaluation of the impact of D_i^{eff} was complemented by a sensitivity analysis on C_{ct} , due to the well-known effect of local capacitances on the characteristic resistive frequencies and shape of Nyquist spectra [88–90].

Figures 7(a) and (b) show the evolution of the Nyquist plots obtained at 750 °C, $P_{O_2,in} = 0.21$ atm when sweeping D_i^{eff} between $2.37 \cdot 10^{-6}$ and $2.37 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ in the EL model. It can be pointed out that the hedgehog shape characteristic of Gerischer behavior does not change until D_i^{eff} is lowered down to $2.37 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$. Therefore, the impact of the gas diffusion resistance would require a three-order magnitude decrease in the value of D_i^{eff} , before being distinguishable as a deconvoluted contribution in the Nyquist plot. Under this scenario, the electrochemical behavior of the MIEC electrode would be severely impacted by its microstructural properties, according to the close link between microstructure and $D_{K,i}^{eff}$, reported in equations (7) and (8). In particular, the electrode performance can be affected either by extremely large τ_{pores} ($\sim 10^3$) or very low ε_{pores} and \bar{r}_{pores} ($\sim 10^{-3}$, $\sim 10^{-3} \text{ } \mu\text{m}$) values. However, the resulting electrode design would include a negligible amount of porosity, thus recalling the microstructure of a dense layer. In conventional ceramic routes, such as tape casting or screen printing, the gas diffusion channels are usually shaped during the sintering step, when the slip additives added in the initial ceramic suspension burn out at a high temperature [91–93]. The τ_{pores} , ε_{pores} and \bar{r}_{pores} values estimated for the manufactured SBCCO electrodes (table 2) lie in the typical range found in the literature for homogeneous SOC air electrodes. Therefore, they are not expected to trigger the low-frequency resistive contribution observed in the experimental data.

Figure 7(c) shows the impact of C_{ct} on the simulated EIS data at 750 °C, $P_{O_2,in} = 0.21$ atm, sweeping the global capacitance in the range 0.45–45 $F \cdot m^{-2}$. The resulting Nyquist plots show that the shape of the curves remains unchanged, thus not highlighting any additional low-frequency resistive contribution. The DRT spectra evidence that the characteristic frequency of the largest peak is shifted to lower values when increasing C_{ct} . Specifically, the simultaneous charge transport and distributed electrochemical reactions

taking place in the electrode bulk of the MIEC material co-limit its electrochemical performance and give rise to partially convoluted resistive processes. The variation of C_{ct} only affects the global reaction mechanism in the transient state, thus not separating the resistances associated with the two physical processes, but only shifting the relaxation time of the convoluted HF peak.

From a more general perspective, the sensitivity analyses evidence that gas diffusion does not limit the performance of screen-printed MIEC electrodes in the investigated operating conditions. As long as the microstructural properties of the manufactured tapes approach those obtained in conventional sponge-like layers, the gas diffusion resistance can be neglected compared to the charge transport and kinetic contributions. Furthermore, the thickness of the state-of-the-art air electrodes is usually smaller (30–50 μm [5, 74]) compared to the one of the typical fuel electrodes, which range between 200 and 300 μm [5, 10, 33]. Thus, their lower thickness reduces the gas diffusion pathway, facilitates the penetration of O_2 and lowers the impact of the microstructural properties on the effective gas diffusion coefficients.

3.2.1.2. Simulated EIS data—GC model

In light of the obtained results, the physical source lying behind the experimental low-frequency peaks was sought by evaluating the impact of gas transport in the gas channels. Specifically, the GC model was constructed with the purpose of reproducing the SBCCO dynamic behavior by adding the contribution of gas conversion (equation (14)) to the physical framework. Figures 8(a)–(f) show the EIS spectra in the 650 °C–750 °C range at $P_{O_2,in} = 0.21$ atm, obtained when computing the GC model and reporting both the Nyquist and DRT plots.

Although the accuracy of the GC model can be further improved at high frequencies by an elementary description of the reaction pathway (as previously discussed in 3.2.1.1.), it can be clearly observed that an LF resistive contribution appears at all temperatures for the GC simulated data. Their characteristic frequencies are in line with the experimental ones, being $LF_{exp,650} = 0.29$ Hz, $LF_{exp,700} = 0.39$ Hz, $LF_{exp,750} = 0.27$ Hz; $LF_{GC,650} = 0.28$ Hz, $LF_{GC,700} = 0.66$ Hz and $LF_{GC,750} = 0.44$ Hz. A good accordance with the relaxation times was obtained calibrating the value of V_{cstr} , which was eventually set equal to $7 \cdot 10^{-7}$ m^3 , thus being consistent with values previously reported in the literature (i.e. set in the 10^{-6} to 10^{-8} m^3 range) [28, 75]. Specifically, V_{cstr} refers to the volume of the gas chamber in which the electrochemical process is assumed to induce concentration changes [41]. As well reported in the literature [40, 41], the gas conversion resistance impacts the electrode performance due to the change in gas composition driven by the electrochemical reaction (i.e. by the net current density). When the electrode shows high electrochemical performance (as for the tested SBCCO material), the current perturbation adopted for the impedance measurements can be found to be sufficient to highlight a resistive contribution in the EIS spectra. Gas conversion is a reversible thermodynamic loss, arising in any SOC system when the electrochemical reaction is taking place, depending both on the current density and the inlet flow rate. Considering equation (14) and the interpretation of Bessler [41], the extension of the gas conversion resistance is driven by the value of F_{inlet}^{tot} . In particular, when

increasing $F_{\text{inlet}}^{\text{tot}}$, the source term (represented in equation (14) by $|N_{\text{O}_2}(t, z = 0)| \times A_{\text{electrode}}$) provides a progressively lower impact on the mass balance, thus resulting in a smaller contribution to the EIS spectra. Therefore, the gas conversion resistance arises from the finite gas supply in the flow channel, extending the concentration changes to the whole gas chamber [41].

The main difference between the EL and GC models lies in the description of the gas supply and conversion in the gas chamber over the electrode. The EL framework models an ideal gas supply followed by finite transport described by Fick's law in the electrode domain (equations (5) and (6)). However, the GC model does not assume an ideal gas supply but takes into account the concentration gradient induced by electrochemistry. In particular, the CSTR model allows us to compute the boundary conditions in terms of partial pressures applied on the electrode surface, which differ from the inlet $P_{\text{O}_2, \text{in}}$ values depending on the operating conditions (i.e. on the current density and $F_{\text{inlet}}^{\text{tot}}$ values).

The impact of gas conversion on the dynamic response of SOC electrodes was included in multi-physics models by previous works, analyzing both complete and half electrolyte-supported cells [28, 67, 75]. Specifically, Effori *et al* [28] focused on LSCF and LSCF-CGO electrolyte-supported cells and showed an increasingly higher impact of gas conversion on the global R_p when raising the operating temperature, thus following the same trend reported in figure 8 for the SBCCO electrode. Furthermore, in the work of Effori *et al* [28], the impact of gas conversion became distinguishable as a separate semicircle in the Nyquist plot when the measured R_p decreased down to $\sim 0.1 \Omega \cdot \text{cm}^2$. The same behavior was obtained for SBCCO, thus showing that the change of the gas composition over the electrode volume becomes increasingly limiting at higher electrode performance. Figures 9(a)–(f) show that the GC framework can also reproduce the LF arcs of the Nyquist plots for different $P_{\text{O}_2, \text{in}}$ values at 750 °C.

The good accordance with the experimental and simulated LF values is confirmed when varying the $P_{\text{O}_2, \text{in}}$ value, being $LF_{\text{exp}, P_{\text{O}_2} = 0.1} = 0.52 \text{ Hz}$, $LF_{\text{exp}, P_{\text{O}_2} = 0.21} = 0.27 \text{ Hz}$, $LF_{\text{exp}, P_{\text{O}_2} = 1} = 2.18 \text{ Hz}$ and $LF_{\text{exp}, P_{\text{O}_2} = 0.1} = 0.81 \text{ Hz}$, $LF_{\text{exp}, P_{\text{O}_2} = 0.21} = 0.44 \text{ Hz}$, $LF_{\text{exp}, P_{\text{O}_2} = 1} = 5.2 \text{ Hz}$. The first description of the gas conversion contribution was provided by the model of Primdahl and Mogensen [40]. In particular, three-electrode measurements on Ni-YSZ electrodes were performed, keeping the potential of the reference electrode independent of the gas phase concentration at the working electrode. The observed low-frequency resistive contribution is associated with very high capacitance values (in the $\sim 10 \text{ F} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2}$ range), thus not being ascribable to interfacial or adsorption processes. Consequently, they attributed the LF resistive contribution to the bulk process, i.e. gas conversion in the gas chamber over the electrode [40]. Large capacitance values were also obtained from the construction of an equivalent circuit fitting the experimental data measured on SBCCO electrodes. Specifically, when varying $P_{\text{O}_2, \text{in}}$ at 750 °C, capacitance values in the 30–70 $\text{F} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2}$ range were estimated, thus being of the same order of magnitude as those reported by Primdahl and Mogensen [48, 49]. This latter observation, combined with the sensitivity analysis performed

on D_i^{eff} , reinforces the assumption that it is associated with the observed LF contribution to the gas conversion bulk process.

The GC framework is tailored to the microstructural properties of the screen-printed electrode and highlights that its dynamic response is subjected to the impact caused by the operating conditions on the gas concentration changes. In other words, the identification of the physical mechanism lying behind the LF peak shows that the electrode microstructure is able to effectively sustain the high electrochemical properties of SBCCO, facilitating gas diffusion through sponge-like porosity. Nonetheless, it can be remarked that additional concentration losses might arise from the flow configuration of the testing setup. In particular, the addition of electron conducting layers over the electrode surface (i.e. metallic felts and ceramic current collectors) can induce a concentration gradient stemming from finite gas transport [41], thus potentially coupling irreversible concentration overpotentials to reversible gas conversion losses. Therefore, the electrochemical properties measured on SBCCO can be enhanced by a proper design of the gas diffusion chamber combined to higher F_{inlet}^{tot} values. It must also be remarked that, from the integration of the LF peak in the DRT spectra of the real data, its value was estimated in the 0.005–0.007 $\Omega\cdot\text{cm}^2$ range. The obtained results show that the testing parameters used for the EIS measurements can have a notable impact only when the electrochemical performance of the analyzed material is highly promising, thus further stressing the inherent potential of SBCCO as an air electrode material for SOCs.

It should be pointed out that the obtained results remain valid in the investigated operating conditions. The impact of gas diffusion on the performance of SOCs is well documented in the literature and microstructural optimization with low-cost substrates is regarded as a key direction to develop high-performing cells [94]. In particular, different manufacturing techniques have recently been studied to tailor the shape of the gas diffusion channels and boost the mass transfer [12–14, 94]. Slow gas transport can drive the establishment of large concentration overpotentials and, in long term operations, promote degradation processes such as electrode delamination (at the air electrode) or Ni re-oxidation (at the fuel electrode) [10, 95–97]. Therefore, the simulations performed by the EL and GC models are not intended to provide a general interpretation of LF peaks observed in the EIS spectra of SOC electrodes. However, they outline the impact played by gas conversion on high-performing air electrodes in the presented operating conditions.

4. Conclusion

This study presents and validates an electrochemical model for high-performing SBCCO-based air electrodes. The numerical framework is used to unravel the physical mechanisms lying behind the resistive peaks observed in experimental EIS data, focusing on the clarification of the origin of the low-frequency contribution. For the first time, a 1D continuum model is developed on SBCCO electrodes, using as inputs

the microstructural properties extracted from the analysis of the screen-printed electrodes. Specifically, the latter were evaluated by combining the statistical analysis of 2D SEM images and an RF microstructural model (previously validated for SOC electrodes) able to simulate the 3D reconstruction of the SBCCO manufactured electrodes. The physical-based model was thus tailored to the SBCCO characteristics and used to simulate its stationary and dynamic behavior in the range 650 °C–750 °C and 0.1–1 atm $P_{\text{O}_2, \text{in}}$.

The 1D electrochemical framework adopts a simplified reaction mechanism, using a phenomenological kinetic rate stemming from the Butler–Volmer formalism to reproduce the global charge-transfer reaction occurring at the SBCCO-porosity interface. A single kinetic constant is used to simulate the electrode performance in the vicinity of the OCV, focusing on the analysis of the stationary electrochemical behavior between -0.1 and $0.1 \text{ A}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ and the dynamic response at OCV. A set of kinetic parameters (E_a , k_{00} , m and $\alpha_{\text{ox/red}}$) is extracted by fitting the I – η curves using an iterative procedure. A good accordance with the simulated and experimental curves is obtained for any investigated operating condition, measuring a root-mean square deviation between 0.006 and 0.02. The model was further validated by coupling the stationary framework with a time-dependent one to reproduce the dynamic behavior of SBCCO electrodes. Specifically, two different models were developed, differing in the description of the gas supply during operation. The EL framework was built assuming an ideal gas supply able to maintain a constant concentration of the reactants over the electrode surface during operation. Instead, the GC model evaluated the impact caused by gas conversion, i.e. the thermodynamic loss arising during operation and related to the finite supply of the gas channels over the electrode surface. Specifically, under the assumption of low current density, the latter were modeled as a CSTR, setting V_{cstr} as the fitting parameter.

A substantial difference was observed in the simulated data obtained from the EL and GC framework. In particular, the EIS data of the EL model do not highlight any LF resistive contribution which, instead, can be observed in the experimental data. A sensitivity analysis on D_i^{eff} revealed that no significant LF contribution arises until D_i^{eff} is lowered down to $\sim 2.37 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2\text{s}^{-1}$. This result evidenced that gas diffusion is not the physical mechanism lying behind the LF resistive peak. Instead, an LF resistive peak is outlined by the EIS data obtained from the GC framework. The CSTR model was found to accurately describe the dynamic behavior of SBCCO at low frequencies when setting $V_{\text{cstr}} = 7 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ m}^3$. Specifically, the gas conversion is identified as a physical process inducing concentration changes that affect the electrode dynamic response. The impact can be observed in the Nyquist plots at OCV due to both the high performance of SBCCO and the flow configuration of the testing setup.

From a broader perspective, the GC model was found to fit with good confidence the SBCCO electrochemical behavior by using the same kinetic parameters extracted from the stationary fitting and setting C_{ct} in the 2 – $10 \text{ F}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$ range, respectively. However, the complex shape of the experimental SBCCO Nyquist plots is not entirely captured by the model, leaving room for further optimization regarding the detailed description of the high-frequency mechanisms. In particular, the highly promising properties of SBCCO will be further studied in composite electrode architectures and in complete cells. Specific investigations will also target the evaluation of intrinsic material properties, such as the concentration of vacancies and their diffusion coefficients. Therefore, the framework presented in this study will be refined with the purpose of detailing an elementary reaction mechanism and upscaling the model to achieve complete cell operation.

Data availability statement

The data cannot be made publicly available upon publication because they are not available in a format that is sufficiently accessible or reusable by other researchers.

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